

D6.2 Plan for the Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication of Results (PEDR1), including Communication Plan (CP)

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Table of contents

Key takeaway messages	4
Summary.....	4
List of abbreviations	5
1 Introduction	6
1.1 Communication.....	6
1.2 Dissemination	9
1.3 Exploitation	9
2 Stakeholder groups.....	10
3 Knowledge outputs	15
4 Tools and channels.....	17
4.1 Project website	17
4.2 Promotional materials.....	17
4.3 Infographics and factsheets.....	17
4.4 Videos and podcast	18
4.5 Press releases.....	18
4.6 Newsletter.....	19
4.7 Social media	19
4.7.1 Social media platforms	19
4.7.2 Social media resources	20
4.7.3 Social media campaigns	21
4.8 Scientific publications	23
4.9 Open-access collections.....	23
4.10 Practice abstracts	23
4.11 Policy briefs.....	24
4.12 Training activities	24
4.13 Participation at external events.....	24
4.14 Synergy-building	26
4.15 European services	26
5 Implementation plan	27
6 Outlook	31
7 References	32

Key takeaway messages

- It is the purpose of this deliverable to outline the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities accompanying the FORSAID project.
- In addition to an introduction of these three spheres of action (Chapter 1), the document also incorporates an overview of the stakeholder groups (Chapter 2), knowledge outputs (Chapter 3) and the formats (Chapter 4) they bear relevance to.
- Building on this foundation, D6.2 also sets out an implementation plan with strategic Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to guide the various dimensions of its execution.
- The PEDR and CP will be subject to updates in M24 and M36.

Summary

D6.2 sets out the strategic approach to communication, dissemination and exploitation activities that will guide the FORSAID project throughout its 42-month duration. Its basis is found in both established European Commission guidelines and extensive consultations across the project's consortium on the topic. The comprehensive and coherent plan at its core is meant to facilitate the efficient maximisation of FORSAID's impact in relation to engaging relevant and diverse audiences.

To that end, D6.2 regards the seven primary stakeholder groups first identified in the project's grant agreement in depth and identifies the constituent sub-groups, key outreach messages and knowledge outputs they correspond to. This is complemented by a list of tools and formats that will be employed to raise awareness, build networks and establish synergies throughout FORSAID's duration. Finally, all the preceding information is incorporated into a detailed implementation plan that sets specific benchmarks on the road to the successful realisation of the aims behind the PEDR and CP. These will be subject to two updates as FORSAID progresses - one in M24 and one in M36.

List of abbreviations

AI: Artificial Intelligence

CDE: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

CP: Communication Plan

EIP-AGRI: European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability

EU: European Union

KER: Key Exploitable Result

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

PEDR: Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

REA: Research Executive Agency

RIO: Research Ideas and Outcomes

1 Introduction

The success of any research endeavour under the umbrella of the Horizon Europe programme depends on establishing communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) guidelines that are marked by clarity, precision and relevance. At all stages of the project's implementation, FORSAID will be assisted by an outreach strategy that is fit for this purpose, thereby facilitating the circulation and utilisation of outputs across and beyond stakeholder networks.

To ensure this outcome, a two-stage process was put in place during the preparation of the present document. First, individual members representing all research groups of FORSAID's consortium were approached during the project's kick-off meeting (M1) for an initial sampling of overarching CDE needs and aspirations. Building on this, a comprehensive CDE questionnaire was circulated among all partner organisations in M2 in an attempt to gauge their needs in this regard more precisely. Within it, participants were prompted to elaborate on the results and outputs they are to be involved in as part of FORSAID's implementation. Subsequently, they were asked to specify the CDE formats, channels and methods they would like to take advantage of with regard to both their specific work and the larger project.

Taking the survey's outcomes and the stipulations of the grant agreement into account, the present report is meant to provide a basis upon which CDE activities would be planned and executed. Prior to exploring those in greater detail, however, it is crucial to differentiate and specify vis-à-vis the definitions of the three core components of the strategy.

1.1 Communication

For the purposes of projects funded under the Horizon Europe programme, the Commission's Research Executive Agency (REA) equates communication with attaining visibility (European Commission, 2025). In that sense, this document takes the term to signify the sum total of strategic and targeted activities that are designed to promote FORSAID to a variety of general audiences. Bearing this in mind, the project is seeking to attain a substantial societal reach by stimulating awareness and interest alike across the public domain. In terms of messaging, FORSAID zeroes in on the importance of technology-driven solutions, plant health measures and stakeholder cooperation to the conditions defining forested areas.

Extending from the very beginning of the project to beyond its conclusion in 2028, communication efforts associated with FORSAID will have the following objectives:

- awareness-raising among stakeholders vis-à-vis project results
- dissemination of information regarding news and events of interest
- facilitation of an active dialogue with and across stakeholder groups
- improvement of the public's general knowledge regarding the issue of forest pest proliferation and the importance of plant health
- presentation of emerging technologies and their prospective role in the pursuit of pest control in forests
- assistance in harnessing the potential of citizen science to address pest-related realities on the ground in forests
- inspiration of cooperation and synergies between interested parties with regard to the project's subject matter
- inception of a stakeholder community that would uphold and carry on the project's vision beyond the date of conclusion

Each objective will be pursued via a designated set of target-group-specific channels, materials and formats. Those will include:

- promotional materials such as flyers, brochures, roll-up banners, stickers, etc.
- regular updates of the news content on FORSAID's [website](#)
- publication of press releases on science news portals (e.g. [EurekAlert!](#) and [AlphaGalileo](#))
- a consistent social media presence and engagement on [LinkedIn](#) and [Bluesky](#)
- outreach to traditional media and topic-specific outlets (e.g. the [Forests Pests Europe newsletter](#) and the [Plant Health Centre newsletter](#))

Already existing or potential bi-directional channels of communication between members of the consortium and relevant external actors are essential to FORSAID's efforts and must therefore be nurtured. Table 1 provides a non-exhaustive list of such outside entities along with their synergy potential in the context of the project. The core criterion behind this selection is the convergence with focus activities and areas of interest characteristic of the FORSAID project. Those include, but are not limited to: **plant protection, technology-driven pest monitoring and control, forest management, agroforestry solutions and geosciences.**

Table 1: Relevant external actors for bi-directional communication activities

Category	Name	End of duration (if applicable)	Potential joint communication activities
Research projects	Biovexo	31 December 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint news items on project websites • Joint press releases • Joint social media campaigns • Joint participation at external events (via dedicated showcase sessions and/or dissemination stands) • Joint webinars and / or training sessions • Guest appearances on FORSAID's podcast
	ADOPT-IPM	30 November 2026	
	PurPest	31 December 2026	
	SUPPORT	31 December 2026	
	ForestPaths	28 February 2027	
	SafeWax	28 February 2027	
	BioAgora	30 June 2027	
	Cerberus (sister project)	31 December 2027	

	STELLA (sister project)	31 December 2027	
	NextGenBioPest	29 February 2028	
	OneSTOP	30 June 2028	
	Sagropia	31 December 2028	
Organisations	The Nature Conservancy	Non-applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation of experts to webinars and/or training sessions • Participation at external events organised by said entities • Guest appearances on FORSAID's podcast • Interaction with said entities' social media posts and campaigns
	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations		
	European Plant Science Organisation		
	U.S. Department of Agriculture		
	European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation		
	European Geosciences Union		
Networks	Forest Information System for Europe	Non-applicable	
	Forest Research		
	International Plant Protection Convention		

1.2 Dissemination

Once again following the definition set out by REA, dissemination activities are conducive to “sharing research results with people who can best make use of them” (European Commission, 2025, 1). In other words, these are efforts guaranteeing the public availability of any and all outputs generated by the project to the relevant stakeholders and potential end-users at each successive stage of implementation. In this sense, dissemination campaigns will commence at the moment when the first project results are accessible. Uni- and bi-directional dissemination channels alike will be employed as part of this effort and will proceed in four outreach dimensions - science, business, policy and the public sphere.

In terms of dissemination defined by a singular direction, any publication activity associated with the FORSAID project will adhere to a strict open-access policy. Naturally, this signifies the full disclosure of all available information on FORSAID’s official website. Furthermore, the consortium remains committed to seeking out high-impact open-access journals (e.g. Research Ideas and Outcomes (RIO)) and trusted public repositories (e.g. the Horizon Results Platform and Knowledge4Policy) for the submission of its outputs. Format-wise, the technical nature of the project is conducive to relying on certain types of dissemination materials. Chief among them will be policy briefs (D6.5) outlining the integration of innovative technologies in the forest pest control sector. Targeting decision-makers at various levels of authority, those reports will contain analyses of the costs and benefits of such deployment on European soil. Tutorial videos will also be distributed to showcase the practical application of the digital solutions in question. Other hands-on materials such as podcast episodes and infographics will also be taken advantage of in the dissemination phase.

When it comes to bi-directional targeting, specific audiences will be identified and invited to engage in the activities surrounding the project’s implementation. This reflects the goal of WP5 in that stakeholders are reached out to in an effort to establish a community of practice that would carry the mission and vision of the project forward. Collaborations at various scales will therefore be pursued with organisations, networks and other projects of interest (refer to section 1.1.) in the form of joint releases and events (webinars, workshops, etc.). This will help establish a continuous and fruitful dialogue on the basis of lasting partnerships. It is namely such connections that will not only ensure the presence of numerous insightful perspectives as the project comes together, but also that the produced results will be in line with the expectations of those that will eventually be entrusted with them.

1.3 Exploitation

Finally, the practical application of FORSAID’s attained results, be it in a policy, research or commercial setting, falls under the umbrella of what REA designates as exploitation activities (European Commission, 2025). In that sense, the actual wider deployment of the project’s envisioned early pest detection framework and any of its complementary technological tools remains a core concern for the publication effort. Dedicated occasions during which this may be accomplished will be organised - examples here include, but are not limited to, Policy Labs and Demo Cases.

Furthermore, opportunities for even greater prioritisation of the project’s results will be pursued, especially in the context of the European Union’s (EU) research popularisation infrastructure (refer to sub-section 4.15) to ensure application well into the future.

2 Stakeholder groups

Any comprehensive PEDR and CP requires a thorough understanding of the core stakeholder groups towards which the project will be targeted. In the case of FORSAID, preliminary stakeholder groups were singled out within the project's grant agreement. Subsequently, the CDE survey undertaken within the consortium allowed for those to be broken down into their respective subgroups (Table 2). Moreover, the questionnaire also gave partners the opportunity to formulate key messages of the project that would target one, several or all of those stakeholder groups (Table 3).

List of core stakeholders:

- Policy and advisory actors (PA)
- Plant protection stakeholders (PP)
- Research and technological developers (RTD)
- Forest industry professionals (FP)
- Plant businesses and plant protection services/products (BPP)
- IT consultants and technology experts (IT)
- General public (GP)

Table 2: Stakeholder groups and subgroups

Stakeholder Group	Subgroup	Relevant stakeholders	Examples
PA	Governance actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest policy departments and actors at the national and European scale • EU-level innovation partnerships • Non-governmental organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission and its relevant Directorates-General (e.g. AGRI; SANTE) • European Parliament • Intergovernmental panels • National parliaments • Elected regional and local councils • European Environment Agency • EIP-AGRI Network • Forest Stewardship Council • Programme for Endorsement of

			Forest Certification <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • U.S. Department of Agriculture
PA	Representational bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landowners' associations • Operational groups in the agroforestry sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European State Forest Association • Confederation of European Forest Owners • Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners • Federation for Forest Communities
PA	Policy partner organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant protection organisations • Forestry consulting enterprises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Forest Institute • European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization
PP	Plant protection activists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant protection organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organisation
PP	Quality control bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Border authorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FRONTEX
PP	Forest areas supervisors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land managers of restored natural habitats • National and local forest services (FP) • Plant health inspectors • Forestry consultants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant Health and Seeds Inspectorate • Plant Protection and Safety of Vegetable Products • State Inspectorate, Sector of Agriculture and

			Phytosanitary Inspection
RTD	Research and technological development actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic and research professionals • R&D companies • EU projects • National laboratories • Research institutes • Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest-based Sector Technology Platform • STELLA (sister project) • Cerberus (sister project) • SafeWax • SAGROPIA • BIOVEXO • ForestPaths • ADOPT-IPM • PurPest EU • NextGenBioPest • OneStop
FP	Forestry industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private forest enterprises • Forestry growers and nurseries • Wood-chain economic actors • Forest association companies • Pulp industry • Technical staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual forest and landowners • Sawmills • Timber, pulp paper, biomass and fibre production facilities • Woodfuel production facilities • Forestry investors • European Panel Federation • Confederation of European Paper Industries • European Man-Made Fibres Association • Bioenergy Europe • European Organisation of the Sawmill Industry • European Confederation of

			Woodworking Industries <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viveiros Aliança • Viveiros do Fradouro • The Sado Valley Forestry Producers Association • APCOR • Asia-Pacific Forestry Commission
BPP	Plant retailers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant traders • Plant importers / exporters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plants for Europe • Flora of Europe
BPP	Plant protection enterprises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated plant protection companies • Regional phytosanitary service • Plant protection product suppliers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CropLife Europe • Natural Plant Protection • National Plant Protection Organisation
IT	Remote sensing companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satellite surveillance enterprises • AI consulting services • App developers for plant health • Remote sensing technicians 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helios Remote Sensing Systems • EARSC
GP	Public in general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen scientists • Nature recreationists • Any additional societal stakeholders • Hiking associations • Visitors of green areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laypeople • End users of wood products
GP	Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science news agencies • European and local media outlets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AlphaGalileo • EurekAlert • ScienceDaily • Phys.org • The Guardian

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Brussels Times
GP	Civil society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental protection organisations • Environmental education organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pesticide Action Network Europe • Climate Action Network Europe • WWF • Friends of the Earth Europe • Generation Climate Europe • FERN

Table 3: Key messages and relevant stakeholder groups

Key message	Stakeholder group(s)
FORSAID will introduce an early forest pest detection system that allows for faster, easier and less time-consuming quarantine pest identification.	PP; BPP
FORSAID will put forward an early forest pathogen detection system underpinned by innovative digital tools.	PP; BPP
FORSAID will provide such instruments based on automatic devices and artificial intelligence for a quick and efficient approach to the detection of forest pests that can be integrated into management plans in the public and private sectors.	FP; IT; RTD
FORSAID will validate the concept of area-wide monitoring of economically important forest pests for prevention and eradication purposes.	PA
FORSAID will establish an ongoing dialogue with stakeholders to identify and co-create the most relevant digital solutions for monitoring regulated forest pests in Europe.	PA; PP
FORSAID will put forward citizen science tools for any citizen to contribute to the early detection of pest outbreaks and learn to recognise forest insects.	GP

3 Knowledge outputs

FORSAID's lasting contribution to forest protection will be an early detection system for pests and pathogens that will be grounded in technological innovation, market-based analyses and stakeholder insights. All the outputs associated with operationalising this aim can be found in Table 4.

Table 4: Central knowledge outputs of the project

Output	Type	Deliverable	Accessibility	Potential Users
Optical markers for agent detection	Publication - report	D2.1	Due M24; website and open-access repository (e.g. Zenodo)	PP; RTD; IT
Drone (RPAS) based warning system	Publication - report	D2.2	Due M30; website and open-access repository	PP; RTD; IT
Infestation - tree level	Publication - report	D2.3	Due M37; website and open-access repository	PP; FP; BPP; IT
Remote sensing of forest pest	Publication - report	D2.4	Due M40; website and open-access repository	PP; RTD; FP; BPP; IT; GP
Image analysis in Trapview	Publication - report	D3.1	Due M34; website and open-access repository	PP; RTD
Metabarcoding e-DNA	Publication - report	D3.2	Due M34; website and open-access repository	PP; RTD

Robot system - identification	Publication - report	D3.3	Due M41; website and open-access repository	PP; RTD; GP
Citizen science database	Data sets	D4.1	Due M28; website and open-access repository	PP; GP
Citizen science guidelines	Publication - report	D4.2	Due M40; website and open-access repository	PP; GP
Stakeholders' opinion	Publication - report	D5.1	Due M7; website and open-access repository	PA; PP; FP; BPP; G
Harmonisation of EU regulations	Publication - report	D5.2	Due M12; website and open-access repository	PA; PP; FP; BPP; GP
Forest value database	Data sets	D5.3	Due M25; website and open-access repository	PA; PP; FP; BPP; GP
Multicriteria ranking	Publication - report	D5.4	Due M30; website and open-access repository	PP
Digital methods for pest monitoring	Publication - report	D5.5	Due M38; website and open-access repository	PA; PP; RTD; FP; BPP; IT; GP

Upon the upcoming update of the CP and PEDR in M24, Table 4 will be expanded to include a list of FORSAID's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the most suitable methods for their

dissemination and application across research, technology and policy. These criteria will be determined based on a questionnaire completed by project partners and will encompass various formats, including policy briefs, academic publications, brochures, factsheets, videos, presentations and workshops.

4 Tools and channels

Throughout its duration, FORSAID will take advantage of a comprehensive set of CDE instruments, harnessing diverse formats and channels to publicise the aforementioned outputs. The tools in question will be both uni- and bi-directional, resting upon established and proven practices in the domain of science communication. The project will also remain cognisant of emerging trends in stakeholder dialogue, which will allow for the seamless integration of new approaches and methods to the strategy. A non-exhaustive list of the tools and channels FORSAID intends to utilise for its CDE efforts includes:

4.1 Project website

As stipulated in project Deliverable 6.1 “*Visual identity, project branding and website*”, a dedicated online domain (www.forsaid.eu) has been established to operate in conjunction with FORSAID’s implementation. On the one hand, it is meant to serve as a central hub of outreach, presenting the project’s vision, mission and objectives to a wider audience. At the same time, the website also represents an open-access repository containing the sum total of all outputs and materials associated with the project that have been finalised. The content of the page will be regularly updated to reflect recent and relevant news, updates and other developments of interest as they arise.

4.2 Promotional materials

A critical component of FORSAID’s CDE strategy, the development of promotional materials will facilitate the presentation of the project’s core messages to a variety of stakeholders by presenting them in an appealing and accessible fashion. Products such as these will also ease other CDE activities such as participation in external events, synergy building and stakeholder engagement as they are distributed across networks, between partners or at conferences.

Examples of promotional materials that will be used during FORSAID’s implementation include:

- project logo
- project one-pager
- introductory presentation
- roll-up banner
- poster
- stickers
- QR codes
- virtual meeting backgrounds
- scientific illustrations of the regulated pest species under investigation

4.3 Infographics and factsheets

Given the multitude of disciplinary, temporal, spatial and technological dimensions of the project, overarching promotional materials need to be supported by more topic-focused outputs. This is the rationale behind the development of infographics and factsheets that will synthesise complex

research efforts on specific subjects. These formats afford the opportunity to present data via an amalgamation of text and visual aids, which will once again ensure the accessibility of the end product as it is showcased to the public. At this stage, the selection of the project's target species, the core categories of tools to be developed and deployed as well as the contributions of citizen science to early detection have been identified as topics in whose context research efforts may benefit from translation into infographics and/or factsheets. These visual outputs will be stored and made available on FORSAID's website and [EPPO's Platform on Communication Material](#). Additionally, they will be distributed physically during relevant events and conferences.

4.4 Videos and podcast

Audiovisual products represent an effective and time-tested medium for communication and dissemination campaigns. FORSAID intends to seize on the opportunities for awareness-raising afforded by these formats by producing general and topic-specific content alike in the project's context. In that sense, videos and a FORSAID podcast will serve to provide an appealing backdrop for presentations on overall aims, distribution of specific outputs and partner interviews. Based on the CP and PEDR survey which was sent out to the consortium, several ideas have already been singled out.

A video on **plant pests and disease symptoms** would be valuable for technicians, young scientists and policy advisors, helping them to identify early warning signs and implement effective management strategies. For researchers, a video exploring **automatic traps and automatic insect identification** could demonstrate how advanced trapping systems and AI-driven identification tools are transforming pest monitoring. Another piece focusing on **eDNA and remote sensing** would show how these cutting-edge technologies enable non-invasive and highly precise detection of pests and plant health issues. Lastly, a video on **smart traps for forest pests**, aimed at practitioners, forest managers and forest associations, would highlight how innovative trapping solutions can enhance early detection and control efforts, contributing to better forest health and sustainability.

With regard to the dedicated project podcast, the production of individual episodes would coincide with the publication of project deliverables and other outputs. In that sense, interviews with various members of FORSAID's consortium would allow for an in-depth exploration of the research tasks and results associated with the various work packages. Furthermore, editions zeroing in on overall progress and lessons learned would underpin annual project meetings and the discussions held there. Finally, the podcast format would also be a valuable tool in relation to synergies with other relevant research projects (both concluded and ongoing). In other words, inviting their own coordinators and task leaders as guest speakers would help showcase how FORSAID is contributing to long-term knowledge transfer and complementarity in the area of forest pest detection.

4.5 Press releases

Press releases are essential to heightening the public visibility of research projects at times of important announcements and updates. Bearing this in mind, FORSAID will utilise two portals for science-based news: [EurekAlert!](#) and [AlphaGalileo](#). These have a two-fold purpose in that they do not merely allow for enhanced communication across the public domain, but also assist with dissemination to the end users of the promoted research. FORSAID's consortium is considering the public launch of the project (via the unveiling of its website), the official publication of core deliverables and the organisation of select CDE activities (such as trainings and workshops) as developments that are suitable for incorporation into press releases.

4.6 Newsletter

A branded newsletter dedicated to the project's implementation will be released on a bi-annual basis. It will have dedicated sections on recent milestones and results, attendance at events and forthcoming endeavours. The newsletter will allow for the cultivation of a network of stakeholders and other interested parties that will further improve the outreach efforts associated with the project. Partners have also identified the possibility of featuring notable FORSAID achievements in IEFC's newsletter 'Planted Forests', thereby increasing project awareness and strengthening synergies.

4.7 Social media

The European Commission's Social Media Guide for Horizon Europe projects states that the employment of this medium allows for an "extremely wide - but also targeted - audience" to be engaged, thereby optimising communication and dissemination activities alike (European Commission, 2023, 5). Consequently, a carefully planned social media presence can greatly enhance the exploitation of research results. Moreover, project representation in such networks is essential to reputation-building and access to relevant scientific debates at the moment of their inception. In terms of synergies, social media can also perform a valuable function, easing the identification of and collaboration with individual or organisational partners.

With this in mind, FORSAID will adhere to a social media strategy in a bid to expand its reach and facilitate network-building on a larger scale in the domain of forest pest control and plant health. The strategy itself, which was developed at the onset of the project, is laid out in subsections 4.7.1. - 4.7.3.

4.7.1 Social media platforms

Ubiquitous presence across all available social networking sites is not a viable option - a careful selection of appropriate platforms needs to be made on the basis of concrete and relevant considerations. Those include the answers to the following questions:

- Does the platform have a sizeable and active general audience?
- Are the project's partners present in and engaging on the platform?
- Are the project's stakeholders represented and active on the platform?
- Are topics relevant to the project being discussed on the platform?
- Does the platform allow for the collection of engagement analytics that will be necessary for reporting?

Taking these factors as well as the research consortium's views on the need to maintain a high ethical standard in the choice of platform into consideration, a decision was made to establish two distinct profiles for the FORSAID project, with the possibility of considering corporate accounts on other networks later on:

- LinkedIn: [FORSAID Project](#)
- Bluesky: [@forsaidproject.bsky.social](#)

The discussion surrounding this selection took into account both the advantages and disadvantages afforded by the chosen websites. Those have been summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Advantages and disadvantages of the chosen social media sites

Social Network	Advantages	Disadvantages
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional focus • Greater leeway in terms of character limits and media attachments • Abundance of thought-leadership content • Ease of access vis-à-vis targeting stakeholders and industrial players • Post-factum editing • Post scheduling • Quote reposting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job search as a primary purpose • Brand-building is time-consuming • Difficulty in popularising corporate accounts • Post expiration after 12 months • Limited interaction opportunities (e.g. polls)
Bluesky	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Navigation between numerous separate thematic feeds • Clear moderation guidelines • Robust screening of disinformation and malicious content • User-friendly operating system • Post scheduling • Quote reposting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low user count due to recent emergence • Limited presence of subject-relevant accounts to engage with • Constraints with character count and media attachments • Post-factum editing impossible

4.7.2 Social media resources

Engagement beyond the confines of the research consortium is considered essential to the success of the social media strategy. For that reason, advantage will be taken of communication channels and profiles whose topics in focus are related to FORSAID's own. In other words, information flows surrounding technology-driven pest control, plant health and innovative forestry solutions will be harnessed. This will involve the identification of both individual, corporate and institutional accounts with relevance to FORSAID's activities. The following among those have already been identified:

- [UN Environment Programme](#)
- [Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#)
- [Forestry Commission](#)
- [International Society for Plant Pathology](#)
- [Global Launch Base](#)
- [EFSA Plants](#)
- [British Society of Plant Pathology](#)

- [American Phytopathological Society \(APS\)](#)
- [IPSN](#)
- [European Citizen Science Association](#)

Beyond those actors, attention will also be paid to relevant research projects that, like FORSAID, are funded under the Horizon Europe programme of the EU. This will be essential to monitoring for notable sector updates and singling out opportunities for synergies. The following is a non-exhaustive list of such projects:

- [STELLA](#) (sister project)
- [Cerberus](#) (sister project)
- [SAGROPIA](#)
- [BIOVEXO](#)
- [ADOPT-IPM](#)
- [PurPest EU](#)
- [NextGenBioPest](#)
- [OneStop](#)

A vital social media resource that will also assist CDE efforts online will be hashtags. In that sense, posts originating from FORSAID's accounts will incorporate relevant hashtags, thereby increasing their reach while also integrating them into networks of related content across the platforms. The following hashtags will be utilised in pursuit of this goal:

- #Forests
- #Pests
- #PlantHealth
- #ForestsEU
- #HorizonEU
- #EUBiodiversity

4.7.3 Social media campaigns

Campaigns are highly effective in ensuring that the messages communicated on social media are both targeting specific stakeholders and focusing on particular relevant subjects. FORSAID is looking to incorporate the following campaigns into its social network communication:

Table 6: Planned Social Media Campaigns

Name	Hashtag	Description	Duration
Meet the project partners campaign	#MeettheFORSAIDPartners	A campaign that will showcase all 17 organisations comprising the FORSAID research consortium.	2 months

Meet the pest species campaign	#FORSAIDPests	FORSAID will take this opportunity to individually present all the EU-regulated pests (fungi, insects and nematodes) that will be covered by the project's research.	1 month
Introducing the work packages campaign	#FORSAIDWPs	The work packages of the project will be presented with their respective aims, tasks and intended outputs.	1 month
Project fieldwork	#FORSAIDFieldwork	This campaign will bring the numerous dimensions of the project's fieldwork into focus, elaborating on the experimental deployment of innovative technologies in forest biomes.	2 months
Technologies of the project	#FORSAIDTech	Here, the spotlight will be on the innovative digital solutions (satellites, drones, insect traps, DNA barcoding) that the project intends to harness.	2 months
Citizen science in focus	#FORSAIDCitizenScience	Based on produced research outputs in WP4, inspiring contributions from the domain of citizen science will be presented to	2 months

		provide proof of its role in forest pest control.	
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Additionally, campaigns will also take place during the annual meetings of the consortium and, where appropriate, during participation at external events. As the project progresses, more ideas for social media campaigns will be incorporated into the updated iterations of the CP and PEDR in M24 and M36.

4.8 Scientific publications

As necessitated by excellence practices in scholarly research, FORSAID contributors will systematise and submit their outputs for publication in high-impact, peer-reviewed science journals. Open-access editions and repositories will be used in this context, including, but not limited to, NeoBiota, EPPO's Bulletin, Silva Lusitana, Frontiers in Forest and Global Science, Forest Ecology and Management, Agricultural and Forest Entomology, IEEE Access, Forestry Reports and more.

4.9 Open-access collections

In line with FORSAID's commitment to access, visibility and longevity with regard to the knowledge outputs of the project, an outlet will be utilised for all traditional and non-traditional resources associated with the initiative. The consortium has selected Research Ideas and Outcomes (RIO) as the platform wherein such a collection can be established. Throughout the publication process, consortium partners, aided and guided by Pensoft Publishers, will adhere to the principles of open-access research for all outputs and datasets produced as part of the project. Specific reporting forms will be established and made available across the consortium to ensure an efficient and timely collection of crucial information in this context.

4.10 Practice abstracts

The European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) offers the opportunity for further targeted dissemination of project results to stakeholders. Practice abstracts, a short-form and practice-oriented format, will be published on this platform so as to bring FORSAID's insights closer to its intended end users. Three such outputs are foreseen in the project's grant agreement in the form of deliverables 6.3, 6.5 and 6.8, respectively. The reports each will contain will cover the following topics:

Deliverable 6.3 - Practice Abstract A (due M10)

- project presentation
- stakeholders' involvement and needs
- neural network for remote sensing
- Remotely Piloted Aerial Systems for stakeholders

Deliverable 6.5 - Practice Abstract B (due M26)

- e-trapping
- metabarcoding e-DNA
- image recognition via artificial intelligence

- citizen science app

Deliverable 6.8 - Practice Abstract C (due M41)

- multi-criteria analysis
- upscaling from tree to stand
- cost-benefit analysis;
- wrap-up of digital technologies

4.11 Policy briefs

Policy briefs provide evidence-based recommendations to decision-makers involved in sectoral policies. Given that it is FORSAID's ambition to introduce a new early pest detection framework, an effort which would necessarily entail the cooperation of policymakers, the development of a persuasive series of policy briefs is of great significance. Research results will be communicated in this fashion via the Commission's own [Knowledge4Policy](#) platform.

4.12 Training activities

The wide future usage of the project's intended early detection framework and its associated tools is contingent upon stakeholders' understanding of the intricacies of that paradigm. Complementing other efforts to ensure this outcome will be dedicated training sessions, workshops and seminars. Those will centre around the core activity clusters of the project, namely remote sensing technologies, ground detection and citizen science. Hands-on demonstrations and best practice protocols surrounding the digital solutions involved in the project's pest monitoring instrument will be provided as part of this endeavour.

Specific examples related to workshops include, but are not limited to, using spectral information to detect plant diseases, plant disease lab diagnostics, and more. Target groups for those specific workshops are researchers, technicians, advisors, etc. A special emphasis will be placed on early career researchers in the field of forest pest management as a way of ensuring the longevity of the findings and methodologies associated with the project. Complimenting the webinars, promotional materials and infographics could be created based on various outputs to further support members of the target groups. Naturally, all results will be communicated via the FORSAID bi-yearly newsletter, website and social media.

4.13 Participation at external events

Representation at international conferences, summits and symposia is an essential step towards truly a truly transborder awareness-raising campaign. FORSAID will identify and arrange to participate in relevant external events across the globe, thereby accessing new networks of stakeholders and decision-makers. In this context, the aim will be for the project to be represented via formal oral presentations, panel discussions, one-on-one encounters and dissemination stands. So far, the following external events have been identified as potential venues for engagement:

Table 7: External events of interest

Event	Date	Scale
Congress of European Entomological Societies	17-20 March 2025	European
German Entomology Congress 2025	17-20 March 2025	European
14th Conference of the European Foundation for Plant Pathology	02-05 June 2025	European
European Forum on Urban Forestry	03-07 June 2025	European
XXVIII Italian National Congress on Entomology	16-20 June 2025	European
Living Planet Symposium 2025	23-27 June 2025	European
5th International Congress of Biological Invasions	21-24 September 2025	International
Agritechnica	09-15 November 2025	European
ForestSAT 2026	04-08 May 2026	International
Neobiota Congress	September 2026	International
IOBC Congress	January 2026	European
IUFRO Conference	August 2027	International

4.14 Synergy-building

Synergies are apparent in the organisation of joint activities, events and campaigns throughout the duration of the project for the purpose of enhancing CDE results on all sides of the consortium partnership. The contents of Table 2 will be instructive in this regard as the given examples of institutions and actors may serve as a guide as to where to seek venues for collaboration. Particular attention must be paid to projects under the Horizon Europe umbrella with a similar research subject matter such as STELLA, Cerberus, PurPest and ForestPaths. Based on the CP and PEDR survey sent to all partners, several other projects and initiatives have been identified as synergy-productive. These can be divided into two categories:

- media outlets (e.g. [Aboutplants](#), [Sherwood News](#), [The Conversation](#), [L'informatore agrario](#), [Waldwissen](#), [Forest Entomology](#))
- project- and organisation-related outlets (e.g. [ICNF](#), [COST 20132](#), [IEFC Planted Forest Reports](#), [Lviv Regional Phytosanitary Laboratory](#), [EFSA](#), [The Navigation Company](#))

Both categories, as well as other outlets maintained by the aforementioned relevant EU-funded projects, will serve to increase and strengthen FORSAID's overall communication and dissemination efforts. In turn, this will help ensure the accessibility and continued utilisation of the project's results beyond its lifetime.

4.15 European services

A further opportunity for increasing FORSAID's public visibility is afforded by the dissemination and exploitation services of the European Commission. Those can serve to bridge the gap between policy-makers and stakeholders, thereby helping to ensure the project's applicability and longevity across invested networks. The list below singles out such services with particular relevance to FORSAID and how they could potentially be harnessed:

- [Horizon Results Platform](#)

An informational hub centralising and systematising the research outputs emerging from Horizon Europe projects, the Platform would be a crucial space for awareness-raising and network-building in the context of FORSAID. In that sense, a compilation of results in a dedicated space on this website will make it easier for stakeholders and members of the public to explore and share the vision and mission of the project, thereby encouraging engagement within and beyond its duration.

- [Open Research Europe](#)

The principles of open data will be a core consideration throughout FORSAID's implementation, which makes this Commission-managed repository a valuable platform for disseminating project publications. Moreover, Open Research Europe's embedded knowledge transfer via indexing in other trusted databases like Portico and Zenodo will further enable the maximisation of impact at the time of submission and over the long term.

- [The Research and Innovation Community Platform](#)

FORSAID's efforts to establish a network of stakeholders and interested actors in the domain of forest pest control will be complemented by its presence on the Community Platform. Designed to enable collaborations, discussions and exchanges across borders and disciplines, this online space will help the project as it reaches out to professional audiences, organises its own events and contemplates synergies.

5 Implementation plan

The implementation plan (laid out in Table 8) of the FORSAID project links the aforementioned CDE tools and their respective stakeholder groups with the appropriate KPIs as a measure of their effectiveness. A dedicated communications team will undertake the necessary and comprehensive planning, monitoring and updating associated with this plan. Additionally, it will assist with technical, organisational and design specificities related to CDE needs. At the same time, it is the responsibility of all other consortium members to participate in CDE activities related to their specific work and expertise as well as to the project in general. Upon doing so, they will be asked to fill out dedicated reporting forms for the use of the communications team. Within them, they will have the opportunity to provide necessary technical information about their activities that could be used in project materials for public circulation.

Three stages underpin the implementation plan. The division is based upon the expected maturation of the project as foreseen in the grant agreement's Description of Action.

Figure 1: Visual representation of the implementation plan's stages and their focus

The beginning of the project will be marked by the **Awareness raising (M1-M18)** stage. It will focus on making the project known across stakeholder networks and in the public space in general, an effort which will depend on proactive initiation of contacts and community-building.

Continuing into stage 2, **Implementation (M19-M36)**, FORSAID will put an emphasis on dissemination, thereby making sure that outputs are linked to their intended end users. This will be accompanied by a rigorous evaluation of the project's impacts and a further build-up of stakeholder relations. This period will also see the two planned updates of the CP and the PEDR - in M24 and M36, respectively. An opportunity will be taken during those reviews to assess CDE actions so that the core KPIs may be recontextualised for the remainder of FORSAID.

Finally, at the **Exploitation (M37-M42+)** stage, the exploitation of results will be centre stage, with planning for the project's legacy beyond the conclusion date also taking place. This will also mark the time when the early pest detection system, the flagship endeavour of FORSAID, will be made public.

At the moment of its publication, the current output D6.2 provides comprehensive information on the KPIs for the period leading up to the first CP and PEDR update in M24, an evaluation which will entail their revision for the project's remainder.

Being a measure for progress, the KPIs have been designed to monitor the progress of CDE activities and identify room for improvement as the stages unfold. FORSAID selected its KPIs on the basis of the S.M.A.R.T. framework (Doran, 1981):

- **Specific:** What exactly is the goal?
- **Measurable:** How do we know the goal is reached?
- **Achievable:** Are resources available to reach this target?
- **Realistic:** Is this goal worthwhile?
- **Timely:** Is there a timeline?

Table 8: Overview of the CDE tools with KPIs in the lead-up to the first update of the PEDR and CP (M1-M24)

Type of CDE activity	Tool	Stakeholder group(s)	Output KPIs	Outreach KPIs
C & D	Project website	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • News items: 48 • Uploaded documents: 8 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of visitors: 3,000 • Rate of returning visits: 20% • Average session duration: 120 seconds • Geographical distribution: at least 20 countries
C	Promotional materials	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-pagers: 1 • Introductory presentations: 1 • Brochures: 1 • Roll-up banners: 1 • Sticker sheets: 1 • Posters: 1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Downloads: at least 15 per item • Distribution at events: at least 100 per item (with the exception of the roll-up banner and the poster)

C & D	Infographics and factsheets	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infographics: depending on number of identified topics • Factsheets: depending on number of identified topics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infographics downloads: at least 25 per item • Factsheets downloads: at least 25 per item
C & D	Videos and podcasts	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videos: at least 2 • Podcast episodes: at least 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video views: 25 • Podcast streams: 50
C & D	Press releases	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press releases: 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Views on EurekAlert!: 350 • Hits on AlphaGalileo: 350
C & D	Newsletters	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter issues: 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New subscribers: 100 • Open rate: 60% • Link click rate: 50% • Unsubscribe rate: 10%
C & D	Social media networks: LinkedIn and Bluesky	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posts: at least 2 per week • Campaigns: 4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New followers: at least 300 • Impressions: at least 50 per post • Interactions per post: at least 3 per post

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic to website: at least 10% of all website visitors
D	Scientific publications	RTD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New publications: at least 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citations: at least 10 per article Altmetric score: at least 15
D	Open-access collections	RTD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Available documents: at least 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Views: at least 50 per document
D	Practice abstracts	PA; PP; FP; BPP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Practice abstracts: 2 	N/A due to lack of access to EIP-AGRI website statistics
D	Policy briefs	PA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy briefs: 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy briefs downloads: at least 15 per policy brief Distribution at events: at least 50 per policy brief
D & E	Training activities	PA; PP; RTD; FP; BPP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training events: at least 1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendees: 20
D	Participation at external events	PA; PP; RTD; FP; BPP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attended events: at least 5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendees: 500
D & E	Joint activities with other relevant	All	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Joint events: 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Event attendees: at least 200

	research projects		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint policy briefs: at least 1 • Joint news items: at least 3 • Joint scientific publications: at least 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributed policy briefs: 20 • Visits per news item: at least 15 per news item • Citations: at least 10 per scientific publication
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6 Outlook

As the project progresses and its CDE needs evolve and crystallise, an update of the present strategy will become necessary. This will occur at two temporal points, in M24 and M36, reflecting the lessons learned, the feedback given and the realities to which the consortium has had to adapt. As stated in section 3, the knowledge outputs' KERs will be featured in the first update on the basis of a further partner survey.

7 References

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